

Personal growth of social educators in the age of information technology

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ABSTRACT

The study aims to develop an IT-based educational model for the personal development of a social educator: emotional intelligence (EI) and creative abilities. The study took place at L.N. Gumilyov Eurasian National University and K. Zhubanov Aktobe Regional University in Kazakhstan. It involved four moderators of online learning, 62 students majoring in “social pedagogy”; two of the teachers were members of the curriculum development commission. The study used the method of videoconferencing and inferential analysis to examine the relationship between EI and the creative abilities of future social educators in Kazakhstan. The results showed that the respondents had a moderate level of EI with an average value of 3.39. The correlation between EI and the creative abilities of social educators was medium-strong and positive. Results indicate that an increase in the level of EI leads to an increase in creative abilities. The novelty and originality of the study lies in the following aspects: the development of an educational model of personal growth of social pedagogues on the basis of information technologies taking into account EI and creative abilities; the use of innovative methods to study the relationship between EI and creative abilities of teachers demonstrates the use of modern technologies of data collection and identification of correlations between the studied variables, which indicates the importance of the development of EI and creative abilities of social pedagogues.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Digital technologies play a pivotal role in reshaping educational and social practices. Through the utilization of innovative technologies, individuals and groups can actively engage in shaping their own culture, interacting with society and one another. It is for this reason that the context of this research is intertwined with the impact of the digital age on education and the sociocultural milieu, with a focus on the role of social educators within this framework. Contemporary technologies and sociocultural changes

necessitate the enhancement of the research potential of social educators, given their direct involvement in the development of children and adolescents in the era of digital transformation. This article centers on identifying key developmental directions within the educational sphere, encompassing the integration of innovative technologies into the educational process, facilitating the socialization and personal development of educators, perpetually updating educational programs and methodologies, as well as ensuring quality feedback for individual growth.

The era of digitization possesses the ability to influence the cultural fabric of society through the utilization of innovative technologies. This process facilitates the transmission of ideas from one person to another and impacts the social communicative processes [1]. It is precisely for this reason that technologies serve as instruments of influence on the well-being of established communities, contributing to the reduction of societal inequality. The contemporary era determines the research potential growth of a social educator. The main object of a social educator's activities is the child [2]. At the present stage of digital technology development, the needs and requests of children, as well as their opinions and mood, are constantly changing. The influence of the environment, social networks, and innovations all contribute to these changes. The need for the development of the research potential of social pedagogy arises precisely due to the increasing responsibility and emerging societal changes associated with innovative technologies. One of the crucial components of pedagogical education in Kazakhstan is the preparation of social pedagogues in the country's higher educational institutions. The result of this education implies the acquisition of special knowledge and skills by future social educators, social thinking development, personal growth, and an increase in social awareness. These abilities allow teachers to constructively perform their duties following official requirements. The central focus of educational modernization in Kazakhstan lies in professional education to foster the development of proficient specialists who possess the requisite competencies to thrive and excel in the domestic labor market [3]. The central concern revolves around the inquiry into how social educators can effectively navigate the rapidly evolving digital landscape and delineate the specific skills and competencies requisite for this endeavor. This inquiry holds significance in ensuring the proficient engagement of social educators, as their role in fostering the development of children and adolescents in the new era becomes more demanding and intricate.

The globalization of technologies and innovative structures in the sphere of education stimulates the adaptability of education to the current social and economic life of every individual. Such processes in human society necessitate the identification of main directions for evolution in the learning environment. The study is aimed at the development of an educational model for the personal growth of social educators founded upon information technologies, particularly regarding emotional intelligence (EI) and creative capabilities. Within this research, the authors will formulate an educational model for the personal development of social educators based on information technologies while also investigating the degree of correlation between EI and creative aptitudes among social educators in Kazakhstan. The educational process is an interdisciplinary teaching method encompassing formal and informal learning activities: economic, ecological, and social aspects [4]. This approach to education is beneficial as it helps students to uncover their talents and experiences, and utilize existing knowledge, ultimately contributing to an educated society [5]. Technological advancements reveal new horizons of possibilities for communication, information exchange, and social cohesion. However, there is also a negative aspect: the rise of religious and cultural intolerance, along with the emergence of new political conflicts fueled by the use of personal data [6]. Education must find solutions to these issues and consider the diversity of worldviews, exploring alternative knowledge acquisition systems with the integration of digitalization. The practical significance of this article lies in its foundation for the personal growth of social educators in an era characterized by the active formation of information technologies, emphasizing the role of EI and creative abilities.

The 21st century is characterized by information progress, technology, and society. In the era of globalization, communication, and information technologies serve as main instruments for achieving optimal outcomes in all spheres of human life [7]. The incorporation of information technologies plays a crucial role in the reformation of Kazakhstan's education system, as information assumes a paramount significance in driving national progress and nurturing the development of human capital. These processes contribute to the formation of a modern society built upon skills, knowledge, and abilities. Innovative technologies have the potential to accelerate business development and enhance efficiency while also bringing about changes in communication methods and social habits within the field of education [8]. The subject of "social pedagogy" has emerged relatively recently in Kazakhstan, influenced by the social, political, and economic changes occurring in the country. The social pedagogue is a professional whose responsibility entails monitoring the lives of children and youth, addressing various parental issues, assisting children in coping with problems and difficulties and facilitating the interaction between adolescents and law enforcement agencies of the state [9]. As evident from the abovementioned, the role of social pedagogy in the contemporary world is significant, necessitating its thorough study and oversight.

Despite the rapid growth of information technologies and their impact on education and social pedagogy, unresolved theoretical and practical questions persist, warranting further investigation. For instance, how can innovative technologies be optimally integrated into the educational process to achieve optimal outcomes? What are the repercussions of the surge in information technologies and digitization for the interaction between social educators and children and adolescents? What specific skills and competencies must be cultivated among social educators to effectively operate within this new information context? Research endeavors are indispensable to unearth optimal strategies for integrating information technologies into education, along with scrutinizing the influence of digitization on the professional activities of social educators. Such pursuits encompass inquiries into identifying key competencies that social educators should foster to thrive in the contemporary information milieu. These studies could profoundly contribute to comprehending how information technologies and digitization can be effectively harnessed to realize educational and social objectives.

In the context of human resource development, the personal growth of a teacher is still crucial for providing education to students. In the 21st century, knowledge of information technology is one of the main factors contributing to the achievement of these goals. This fact is evidenced by the experience of leading economic systems. Countries with developed economies have invested significant resources in education, thereby creating an efficient, competitive, and sustainable national economy [10]. The conditions of the modern world market confirm the thesis about the decisive role of human capital in the educational well-being of society. The study of human development enters a new era of theoretical and methodological innovations in research and applications [11]. Through interaction with students and their culture, the pedagogue experiences individual growth as a professional. Relationships serve as the primary driving force that influences the quality of education. Assessing and interpreting these relationships can serve as assets in the construction of effective educational programs [12]. One of the reasons for the increasing sociality among teachers is the emergence of informational structures and technologies that enable individuals to explore their interests [13], [14]. Education necessitates conceptually new approaches to the design of instructional processes, as it has transitioned from a closed system with limited access. The sphere of higher education in developed countries emphasizes enhancing the professional competencies of specialists [15]. Due to rapid advancements in the information and technological domains, the skills of young contemporary professionals require constant improvement and development. These skills include critical thinking, problem-solving abilities, information analysis and synthesis, application of personal knowledge in various situations, effective communication with others, self-directed work, and the ability to locate necessary resources and technologies [16]. As a result, the concept of "education for the sake of education" has lost its value, as modern learning approaches demonstrate the employer's needs, with the abovementioned characteristics being focused on the labor market.

Information technologies are changing socioeconomic interactions globally. Technical structures gain significant importance in the labor market, as their objective is to ensure societal quality. Moreover, a key issue arises in reevaluating the pedagogical approach to student learning in the era of digitization. The effective development of professionals and specialists in various fields, along with their individual growth, guarantees a country's competitiveness in the realm of education in the future. As a result, factors are created for social cohesion and the equitable participation of every individual in digital democracy [17].

However, despite the attained successes and revelations, contemporary human development research harbors certain pivotal theoretical enigmas and unresolved debates necessitating further inquiry. Specifically, it is imperative to delve deeper into how educators' engagement with diverse cultural and social contexts impacts their individual growth and professional advancement. What specific interaction mechanisms between teachers and students foster more effective learning and stimulate student personal development? Queries about adapting educational methods and approaches to a diverse student audience remain pertinent. Moreover, subsequent research could focus on investigating effective teaching and knowledge assessment strategies within the new information milieu: how to judiciously combine the use of information technologies with traditional teaching methods; how to evaluate and nurture the development of critical thinking, autonomy, and other essential skills in contemporary settings. Hence, further research in the realm of human development has the potential to propel us forward in comprehending intricate matters associated with interaction, education, and innovations in the information era.

Emotional intelligence, competence of skills, and personal development are professional indicators of a modern teacher who is at the head of the learning process [18]. The interaction of these indicators with innovative technologies affects the competence and personal growth of a teacher. EI, along with creativity, plays a considerable role in the learning process.

Academic training opens up new horizons for professional engagement by seeking contemporary instructional content and innovative learning resources [18]–[21]. Innovative technologies assist educators in personal growth and development while enabling students to think critically, analyze situations, and effectively tackle challenges and problems. Thus, innovative information opportunities and online learning

ensure the following [19]: i) the unity of the educational process; ii) optimal conditions for organizing teacher-student interaction; iii) the systematic learning of the subject content by students; and iv) continuous mastery of culture through the acquisition of the necessary subject knowledge and skills.

The integration of these components into a unified practical system would create educational products that contribute to the personal growth of teachers and broaden the creative abilities of both teachers and students [22]. Education aims to provide individuals with the opportunity for personal development through the exploration of human culture and creative expression. It should also form value orientations and develop abilities. Global conditions and social demands shape the emergence of a new model of education, one that is based on self-regulation factors in the realm of online education and the utilization of information technologies.

It is vital to improve the quality of human potential and provide the future of Kazakhstan with a highly qualified workforce. However, it is possible only if higher education in the republic is modernized and integrated into the global educational space [23]. The sphere of higher education is a priority for the modern economic development of the country. The quality of higher education determines the country's sustainable competitiveness in the context of globalization [24]. The role of intelligence and creativity is continuously growing, along with the significance of science, communication abilities, and humanism. Therefore, the need for special training for professionals increases. The abovementioned training would contribute to the personal growth of individuals, fostering the development of EI and nurturing their creative capacities, consequently leading to the establishment of novel socio-educational circumstances within the context of Kazakhstan.

A study by Kazakhstani scientists aimed to develop an integrated approach to solving the problem of digitalization of education in the Republic of Kazakhstan. To this end, the researchers attempted to identify problems in this area and form priorities and possible ways to solve them [25]. The integration of IT programs into the educational process is transforming the content of subjects, pedagogical requirements, ethics, and student discipline. In the era of digitization, the quality of education becomes a strategic task and a main factor in the successful development of a country's economy. The research uncovers the challenges faced by the present "digital" generation, including dependence on social networks and communication within them. These factors have implications for the acquisition of knowledge and the overall welfare of the emerging generation. One of the primary goals of education, as explored in this study, is the algorithm of educational technologies. This algorithm encompasses skills such as non-standard thinking, a creative approach to problem-solving, and the development of human intelligence and logical reasoning. Therefore, it is essential to assess the effectiveness of implemented programs based on experimental data to formulate requirements for ICT-based education.

Pedagogical science and practice emphasize the problem of students' competency formation. The state compulsory education standard (SCES) for higher professional education in Kazakhstan delineates the framework of novel requisites for the competency-based approach in professional training. This system emphasizes the development of competent professionals in their respective fields. Additionally, the competency-based paradigm in education encompasses personal growth, professional development, moral values, and the role of educators within their environment. All of these factors contribute to meeting the demands of present-day society for future specialists [26].

Despite the achieved accomplishments and in-depth research, certain deficiencies and avenues for further investigation persist within this domain, which could serve as subjects of future theoretical debates and enigmas. Firstly, a more detailed exploration is warranted into methods for the optimal integration of innovative technologies into the educational process. Secondly, it is crucial to investigate the impact of digitization and the utilization of information technologies on social interaction and interpersonal relationships. Thirdly, additional research should be directed towards assessing the effectiveness of innovative educational programs aimed at enhancing the competence of educators and students. Additionally, the study of the influence of digitization on the quality of higher education must continue. Consequently, despite the advancement in educational and digitization research, numerous unanswered questions and challenges remain before researchers and practitioners. These inquiries could form the basis for further theoretical debates and conundrums, contributing to a deeper understanding of the interplay between innovations, EI, and personal growth within the educational context.

The study aims to develop an IT-based educational model for the personal development of a social educator, namely regarding EI and creative abilities. There were two research questions of the study: i) what is the level of EI of social educators in Kazakhstan; and ii) is there a connection between EI, creative abilities, and innovative technologies among social educators in Kazakhstan. Thus, the research objectives are to develop an IT-based educational model for the personal development of a social educator; identify the level of EI among social educators in Kazakhstan; study the level of creative abilities of social educators in Kazakhstan; identify the relationship between EI and the creative abilities of social educators in Kazakhstan.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

2.1. Research design

To examine the correlation between EI and creative capacities among social pedagogues in Kazakhstan, the study utilized video conferencing and inferential analysis as research methodologies. The theoretical framework for developing an education model based on information technologies was derived from the niche construction theory [21]. Building upon this theory, the authors formulated a hypothesis suggesting that the educational environment exerts pressure on pedagogues, prompting them toward self-learning and self-development. Through the socialization of personal and creative qualities, the innovative system influences educators' personal and professional growth. The research method encompassed a competency-based approach that underscored the necessity of concurrently developing emotional and creative abilities. Emotional abilities refer to professional knowledge, skills, and competencies that are required by society to fulfil work responsibilities. On the other hand, creative abilities encompass cultural aspects of work and social habits that align with the development of potential and personal aspirations necessary for employee professional engagement and individual growth [20].

2.2. Participants

The study took place at L.N. Gumilyov Eurasian National University and K. Zhubanov Aktobe Regional University in Kazakhstan. It involved four moderators of online learning, 62 students majoring in social pedagogy; two of the teachers were members of the curriculum development commission, and they conducted training, accepted homework, and assessed the participants. The number of women was 33 people; the number of men was 29. All teachers of the university took part in the study. The average age of the participants was 20.5 years. All teachers had a bachelor's degree and at least seven years of experience; two teachers from the commission had a master's degree. Moderators set up computers helped participants with any problems associated with innovative technologies and uploaded videos to an online learning platform.

2.3. Procedure

The developed educational model is a 3-month five-level online program that allows for gaining experience and personal growth of a social educator. This process involves using EI and creative abilities as shown in Figure 1. The training took place in a group format online via the Moodle platform. The research participants gained practical experience and searched for information to complete tasks in a simulated context using modern information resources and advanced intellectual technologies. Moderators uploaded tasks for teachers in the form of a 10-minute video. Teachers accepted homework assignments during short video conferences, which lasted about 6 minutes. In addition, at the second level of training, a training video was replaced with a training and an online conference.

Figure 1. The IT-based educational model for the personal development of a social educator

Level 1 aimed to identify social educators' problems regarding personal growth and the use of innovative technologies. At this stage, participants watched videos about typical issues and errors when working with computer technologies and learned the possibilities of their solutions. The second task was an online questionnaire. The questions focused on the professional plan of future teachers and their desired achievements. Level 2 of the program included solving the problems. The participants received training on such topics as "Who am I? Where to move on?". The training considered questions about what the future may hold for social educators and their path of professional development. Additionally, an online conference "working with computers and networks" demonstrated the advantages and disadvantages of working with innovative technologies and methods of their application. At this stage, the participants formed the intention

to master professional skills. At Level 3, participants received videos with tasks. They had to practice the material from the first two lessons: identify personal problems in terms of personal growth and with innovative technologies, as well as find ways to solve these problems. The emphasis here was on provoking professional self-interest and strengthening constructive associations with the profession. Level 4 was devoted to the development of personal potential and intelligence. It included four sub-topics: the development of public speaking; the development of organizational abilities; social skills; and professional vision. The moderators uploaded a five-minute video for each sub-topic. Level 5 included videos and tasks for the development of innovative thinking and creative abilities of participants-social educators. The emphasis was placed on creating the flexibility of innovative thinking and ensuring a balance between personal growth and creativity. The information technology-based training system employed a project approach. That is, each task has certain boundaries and evaluation criteria. Moreover, student teachers were not allowed to move to the next level of professional development unless they completed the current stage. Progress assessment took place before and after each assignment to identify learning obstacles.

2.4. Data collection

The collection of respondents' answers was in the form of homework accepted during a video conference. The conferences were conducted after each level for 6 minutes. During these 6 minutes, each participant was required to answer questions concerning a certain module of the developed program. Each homework assignment was rated at a maximum of 10 points. Then moderators and teachers processed the data received from the study participants and assigned them points for tasks. The final procedure was the calculation of the average score of each teacher.

2.5. Data analysis

The data analysis applied the calculation of frequencies, percentages, and the average score of respondents. In this study, the t-test and one-sided ANOVA served as tools to determine whether there were significant differences in the EI levels of respondents depending on the group. The study employed the method of differential analysis (the Pearson correlation) to trace the connection between the EI and creative abilities of social educators in Kazakhstan.

2.6. Ethical statement

This study was developed and carried out after approval by the administration of the educational institution of Kazakhstan. All the participants and administrators followed the research protocol developed before the start of the research activities. Participation in the study was carefully coordinated with all participants. The participant's data were anonymous to other participants of the research process.

2.7. Limitations

This experiment involved only one educational institution in Kazakhstan. Accordingly, the results cannot reflect the results of studying at universities throughout the country. In addition, the number of participants was insufficient to determine the exact level of personal growth of social educators in the conditions of active information technology development. This relatively small sample size may constrain the potential for generalizing the results to a larger population of future social educators. Other researchers could overcome these limitations by undertaking additional measures and enhancing the research method. Increasing the sample size: to ensure more robust outcomes, researchers could expand the student sample and involve multiple educational institutions across different regions of Kazakhstan. This would enable obtaining a more representative sample and augmenting the overall number of study participants. Accounting for participant diversity: to account for gender differences, researchers may strive for equal participation of both sexes in the study. Additionally, demographic characteristics such as age, work experience, and educational level could be considered. Employing a more extended temporal interval: For a more precise exploration of the personal growth of social educators influenced by information technologies, researchers could extend the observation period. This would facilitate tracking changes over a longer duration, resulting in more reliable conclusions.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. The level of emotional intelligence

The results of the analysis show that the respondents (social educators) had a moderate level of EI with an average value of 3.39 as displayed in Table 1. The average of the four categories of EI was at an average level with average values. These categories were emotional self-awareness, emotional self-control, self-motivation, and empathy. One of the EI variables among respondents was at the highest level with an average value of 4.12. This variable was social skills.

Table 1. The level of EI

Variables	SD
Self-awareness	2.71
Self-control	2.89
Self-motivation	3.57
Empathy	3.58
Social skills	4.12
The level of EI	3.39

3.2. The correlation between emotional intelligence and the creative competency

Tables 2 and 3 present creative development that depends on skill levels and personal development. Tables shows that the correlation between teachers' EI and creative abilities was medium-strong and positive. The validation of this finding was substantiated by the correlation coefficient values associated with each category of EI. The coefficient value for all EI was $r=0.641$, $p<0.01$. These results show that an increase in the level of EI leads to an increase in creative abilities.

Table 2. An analysis of the Pearson correlation between EI and creative abilities of social educators

Variables	Creative abilities	
	r	P
Self-awareness	0.205	0.137
Self-control	0.146	0.288
Self-motivation	0.295*	0.030
Empathy	0.668**	0.000
Social skills	0.604**	0.000
The total level of EI	0.661**	0.000

*It is significant at 0.05

**It is significant at 0.01

The results of the study show that the social educators had a moderate level of EI. Social skills were at the highest level, demonstrating the relevance of this EI category in the profession of a teacher. At the same time, the lowest level of self-awareness indicated the opposite. There is a need to improve the educator's knowledge and skills by attending training sessions, professional courses, and other required forms of learning. The appropriate education would positively affect the creative abilities of teachers. There was also some difference in the levels of EI depending on the work experience and higher education of teachers. Thus, university teachers with a high level of qualification tended to have a higher level of EI. The results of the study also confirm that the personal development and creative abilities of social educators were at a relatively high level. This finding suggests that the participants in this study had good competence and personal development skills that contributed to their professional competence. Thus, the level of EI plays a strong, positive, and significant role in the creative abilities of teachers.

The study has unveiled significant aspects of the interrelation between EI and creative abilities among social educators: social educators exhibit a moderate level of EI, with higher scores in the category of social skills and relatively lower scores in the self-awareness category. An observable and significant positive correlation is present between EI and creative abilities, implying that fostering EI could play a role in augmenting the creative aptitude of educators. Professional education and work experience exert an influence on the level of EI among social educators. The personal development of social educators is at a high level, and this has a positive impact on their creative abilities. This study contributes to the literature by providing novel insights into the significance of EI in the context of the creative abilities of social educators. It highlights the significance of nurturing emotional readiness alongside professional skills to ensure effective pedagogical engagement within the context of the digital era. Future research directions encompass investigations into the impact of EI training (additional research could examine the efficacy of educational programs) and analysis of interrelationships with other factors (studies could delve more deeply into other factors beyond education and experience that might influence teachers' EI and how this influences their creative potential). Drawing on the research findings, future research can offer specific recommendations for the development of educational programs and methodologies aimed at nurturing EI among social educators and enhancing their creative capacities.

The updated educational program includes the use of new information technologies in the educational process of primary and secondary schools, as well as universities. It identified the problem related to the development of intellectual skills and creative abilities in the process of teaching and training future specialists in higher education institutions [26]. One of the studied works elaborated an integrated approach to solving the problem of digitalization of education in the Republic of Kazakhstan. The authors

identified problems in this area and formed priorities and possible ways to solve them [25]. The results of the survey revealed the main problems and allowed the researchers to set tasks for deeper study. The study also formed a general idea about the scope of further research and its goals.

Another work assessed the level of EI by the method of Hall. It found significant differences in the EI of representatives of two groups on different scales [27]. The study involved 700 participants from two countries, 350 people from each with approximately equal distribution by gender and age. The paper developed the method for determining the differences in the features of EI. The method can be used to correct the methods of teaching and personnel management in higher educational institutions. The findings can also be valuable for the formation of educational staff in Kazakhstan and Russia. The Fischer transformation on several emotional awareness scales was $f^*_{em}=5.466$. In our study, the results also confirmed relatively high levels of social educators' personal development and creative abilities. This fact suggests that the teachers who participated in this study had good competence and personal development skills that contributed to their professionalism.

Table 3. The Pearson correlation between EI and creative abilities of social educators

Variables	Creative abilities	
	r	P
Self-awareness	0.121	0.378
Self-control	0.115	0.403
Self-motivation	0.410**	0.002
Empathy	0.579**	0.000
Social skills	0.624	0.000
The total level of EI	0.641**	0.000

*It is significant at 0.05

**It is significant at 0.01

Another researcher's work demonstrated the development of intellectual skills among primary school teachers in Kazakhstan [28]. The study explored how innovative student learning influenced the intellectual abilities of their teachers, considering factors such as critical and creative thinking. The author employed quantitative analysis, descriptive statistics, and two tests: the Wilcoxon test and the Mann-Whitney test. The study results validated the positive impact of intellectual training on the experimental group of teachers. After eight weeks of training, the experimental group exhibited an increase in levels of creative, heuristic, and critical thinking. The control group, which received traditional training, showed significantly weaker dynamics compared to the experimental group. The results of our study indicate that participants, who were social pedagogues, have an average level of EI (3.39). The mean values of the examined categories of teachers' intelligence were as: emotional self-awareness 2.71, emotional self-control 2.89, self-motivation 3.57, and empathy 3.58. Social skills exhibited a high level with an average value of 4.12. In a study of Pakistanis based on the knowledge-based view (KBV) concept, the influence of EI, one of the factors contributing to knowledge management, on knowledge management processes (KMP) within research universities is examined [29]. The research investigates the direct impact of knowledge management on the ability for innovative activities. The study was conducted on a sample of 248 individuals, encompassing both academic and administrative staff, from higher education institutions in Pakistan. The relationships were assessed using the structural equation modelling with partial least squares. The obtained findings suggest that EI serves as a favorable factor, making a positive and significant contribution to enhancing the effectiveness of KMP.

Another Kazakh study aimed to assess the problem of developing the EI of future social educators according to the opinions of future social educators [30]. In this scholarly work, the authors employed a qualitative experimental method. The study was conducted during the academic year 2021-2022 in Almaty. The group of participants consisted of 40 educators involved in teaching at the Faculty of Social Sciences. The researchers developed a semi-structured interview form to collect the research data. The results revealed that most of the candidates for teachers had an average level of EI. Most of them also demonstrated behavior that was indicative of high EI. The instructors demonstrated the ability to express their emotions, understood the underlying reasons for their emotional behavior, displayed empathy towards others, and maintained control over their emotional states by expressing their emotions only when necessary. The educators were presented with three distinct categories to evaluate obstacles to emotional development, specifically: familial impediments, personal hindrances, and environmental barriers. Based on the obtained results, the conclusion was drawn that teachers require seminars that emphasize the significance of emotional development for social pedagogues. The empirical research among Chinese individuals aims to investigate the influence of EI on learning outcomes (social, cognitive, self-development outcomes, and university experience satisfaction)

among students in Chinese research universities [31]. The study utilized a sample of 454 students from research universities in China. The research objective was to examine the direct impact of learning outcomes on students' academic performance (cognitive skills and standardized tests). The relationships were examined using the structural equation modelling method with partial least squares. The findings indicate that EI significantly influences learning outcomes.

An essential component of creative and critical thinking is intelligence. Creativity is a facet of the structure that entails the mental skills and intellectual abilities of educators and students [7], [28]. Intellectual abilities are one of the key factors in personal growth, as they unlock individual qualities and influence fundamental processes in the psyche [32]. In another study, researchers examined the direct relationship between the EI of top managers and the quality of strategic decisions made by them their companies [5]. This relationship is further explored through the mediating role of open innovations in the context of intellectual information systems, which can influence how top managers make decisions. The survey method was employed in the research, with data collection conducted through cross-sectional surveys using questionnaires. A final sample of 213 completed questionnaires from managers was obtained and analyzed. According to the hypothesis, there exists a strong positive correlation between the EI of managers and the quality of the strategic decisions they make. Open innovations have revolutionized how banking top managers make decisions that subsequently define policies. Decision-makers must possess decision-making skills while remaining attuned to their surroundings. Consequently, they exhibit EI, and intellectual information systems further amplify this trait.

4. CONCLUSION

The formation of a professional environment of personality-oriented education in universities involves strengthening the socio-pedagogical orientation in the personal and professional development of each teacher. The attainment of a trajectory of self-development, constructed upon individual and professional aspects, is feasible. In this regard, professional education requires active practice-oriented forms and methods of training. The results of the study indicate that social educators have a moderate level of EI. The highest level of social skill competence demonstrates the relevance of this EI category in the profession of a social educator. At the same time, the lowest level of self-awareness indicates the opposite. There is a need for the enhancement of teachers' skills and knowledge, which can be facilitated through professional training and courses. The findings also confirm that social educators' personal development and creative abilities are relatively high. Thus, the teachers who participated in this study had good competence and personal development skills. Enhancing knowledge within educational courses for social pedagogues using digital technologies is one of the opportunities for developing the research potential of educators.

For further research author can conduct the study across multiple educational institutions in Kazakhstan to ensure the generalizability of the findings beyond a single institution. Enlarge the participant pool to obtain a larger and more diverse sample of social educators. This will enhance the statistical power and reliability of the results, allowing for more confident conclusions. Ensure a balanced representation of both male and female educators in the study to capture potential gender-related differences in EI and creative abilities. Collaborate with experts from diverse fields such as psychology, education, and technology to gain a multidisciplinary perspective on the impact of information technologies on educators' personal growth. By addressing these recommendations, future research can build upon the current study's findings and contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of the role of information technologies in enhancing the personal growth of social educators. Thus, the practical significance of the article is in a scientific basis for the personal growth of a social pedagogue in the conditions of active information technology development. At the same time, the emphasis is placed on the role of EI and creative abilities. Hence, in further research, it is necessary to study this topic in other areas of study. Future studies may conduct more continuous observations and involve a larger sample. These approaches would show more accurate data on this issue.

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